

1 **Arid5b is activated early in human embryonic development.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Arid5b
9 as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the
10 human embryo.

11 Citations

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